

Labour shortages in the health care sector in Germany : Implementing targeted immigration policies to attract qualified health care professionals

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Executive summary

When discussing the issue of the healthcare workforce shortage in Germany, there are many challenges that need to be addressed. These challenges are deeper and, in some cases, bigger problems that require a great deal of investment, reform of some government and educational policies, awareness-raising in the population and long-term reform policies. Generally, the challenges of the healthcare workforce shortage in Germany are issues such as the aging or increasing elderly population, the increasing retirement of healthcare personnel and the lack of sufficient replacements, the stressful conditions for healthcare personnel in Germany, Lack of enough capacity to accept medical and health sector students at universities and medical institutes in Germany, obstacles to the integration of foreign personnel in the health sector, government policies. There are solutions to overcome these challenges that require long-term investment and the implementation of new policies that can be useful. The integration of migrant health workers in Germany hospitals faces several challenges. Recruitment processes are largely unstructured and tend to favor candidates who can be easily employed, avoiding administrative obstacles such as work permits and the recognition of foreign qualifications. While individual support measures like assistance with housing or funding for language courses are available, broader support—particularly for family reunification and labor market access for spouses—is still lacking. Language remains a major barrier. Although training programs have been launched to help foreign-trained nurses meet German standards, many participants struggle to pass exams due to limited language skills. Works councils play an important role in supporting migrant workers and addressing workplace conflicts or discrimination, but their efforts are mostly reactive and limited in scope. Legal and regulatory barriers prevent many non-EU migrants from fully entering the labor market or continuing their professional training. Unlike their EU counterparts who benefit from streamlined recognition of qualifications, non-EU professionals must undergo complex and often lengthy evaluation processes. As a result, many migrants work in positions below their qualification level during the recognition phase, leading to underemployment and lower wages .

Context

Challenges and relevant legal and institutional background regarding the Labour shortages in the healthcare sector in Germany :

The problem facing the German health-care system is potential financial collapse. The reasons for this are as follows: (1) a change in the age structure of the population that involves a shift to an increasingly elderly population requiring more medical care without commensurate financial contributions; (2) an increase in non-wage labor cost being part of the social benefits leading to an extremely high work cost, which has resulted in Germany not being competitive within and outside Europe in many areas; (3) a persistently high unemployment rate leading to insufficient contributions to the sickness fund; (4) the financial burdens caused by integration of former East Germany; (5) the relative lack of outpatient surgical procedures (although these are becoming more frequent), duplication of tests because of demarcation between office-based and hospital-based physicians (although this is diminishing), and extensive durations of hospitalization due to per diem reimbursement (a cost-per-case payment, similar to a diagnosis-related group system, is being implemented); and (6) the lack of self-responsibility of the German citizens, who have been pampered by probably the most generous guaranteed health-care package in the world, and their difficulty in giving up benefits that they have enjoyed for years. Germany seems to have a growing recognition that a reform program leading to an overhaul of the financing structure of the health-care system is necessary. Interference by the government to control cost and contribution rates is apparently of only temporary benefit. (Wahner-Roedler et al., 1997). The shortage of general care physicians is becoming noticeably worse – now even in cities. At the same time, many young people are having to give up their career aspirations or study abroad. Experts warn that even doctors from abroad won't be able to fill the gap. (Peters, 2025). The goal of any further reform in the structure of the German statutory health insurance is to create a system that regulates itself and brings medical progress, national economics, and acceptable individual contribution rates in accordance with one another. In January 1996, the Bundestag (Congress) proposed a preliminary draft as the third step of the German health-care reform (the first step was in 1989, and the second step was in 1993). Although this was not approved in its current form by the Bundesrat (Senate), the essential parts are expected to pass. The important points of this preliminary draft are as follows. All further developments in reform of the German health-care system will be based on historical principles and on those previously documented as useful. (a) Solidarity, self-responsibility,

and subsidiarity are and will remain the essential structures of the German health-care system. (b) Social equality will remain between young and old, healthy and sick, poor and rich, and single and married. (c) The health-care system will remain pluralistic, stimulating competition between sickness funds. (d) Medical progress must be financed and made available for the entire population. Self-government will be promoted while stable contribution rates are maintained. (a) The principle of subsidiarity implies that self-administration always has priority over government involvement, as long as the involved parties are able to manage the affairs of the statutory health insurance. Because individual persons are now able to join the sickness fund of their choice (rather than by profession or location), the risk structures of the different sickness funds are balanced, and each sickness fund is involved in self-responsible competition. Work must be done to increase the range of self-government, and mechanisms for conflict management must be developed. (b) Self-administration and self-government must go hand-in-hand with an increase in financial responsibility. Therefore, the requirements for an increase in the contribution rates will be tightened, and the available funds will be used more responsibly and economically. (Wahner-Roedler et al., 1997). In Hamm, ten practices closed within the past year. There's now one doctor for every 1,800 residents, and only 84 percent of the doctor positions are filled. "In nine years, that figure will be 67 percent," says health services researcher Hans-Dieter Nolting, whose IGES Institute conducted the study. According to the study, some medium-sized cities will soon have around 20 percent fewer general practitioners. (Peters, 2025). Increases in contribution rates will be limited to realization of medical progress. Autonomy will be increased by liberalization of contracts between sickness funds and physicians as well as between sickness funds and clients, whereby the principle of solidarity must be maintained. The sickness funds will be encouraged to develop innovative models. The sickness funds will bear the responsibility for maintaining stable contribution rates. As a means to ensure stable contribution rates and to avoid further burdens for employers, increases in contribution rates for administrative developments will be avoided. Increases in contribution rates will be possible only if they are important for medical care and development. Self-responsibility of the insured population will be promoted. (a) The interest of the members enrolled in the statutory sickness fund will be enhanced by availability of the financial aspect of the statutory health insurance. Beginning in 1999, patients enrolled in the statutory health insurance will be able to request information regarding the cost of services received. (b) Partial reimbursement of the paid premium, which has been a feature of private insurance, will be available in the future for participants in the statutory health

insurance. In a preliminary survey of 1,917 insured persons, 71% thought that a partial reimbursement of the premium was reasonable if no or only minimal service had been received during a calendar year. Because a partial reimbursement of the premium cannot be obtained equally by all persons insured (a reimbursement is more likely for young healthy people than for elderly and chronically ill people), this change seems to be an interference in the financing structure of the statutory health system, which is based on the principle of solidarity. (c) Copayments are being considered for inpatient preventive-care services and rehabilitation spas. At regular intervals, these copayments will be adjusted. Beginning in July 1997, the copayments will be adjusted at 2-year intervals, according to the financial experiences of the 2 previous years. Thus far, a Europe-wide health-care system does not exist. The European Community could, however, facilitate the adoption of such a plan by (1) issuing recommendations and directives to achieve harmony of the basic packages of treatments available in Europe, (2) enforcing mandatory health insurance schemes by ensuring that existing members of the European Community maintain a mandatory health insurance scheme and that new members create one as a precondition to membership in the community, and (3) allowing insurance funds to operate across borders. (Wahner-Roedler et al., 1997). Germany's healthcare sector faced a critical shortage of skilled labor, with over 47,400 vacancies unfilled in 2023/2024. The aging population and increased healthcare demands exacerbated the problem, particularly impacting physiotherapists, dental assistants, and nursing staff. This shortage extended beyond healthcare. Some 47,400 positions in Germany's healthcare sector were unable to be filled by suitably qualified applicants in 2023/2024, suggesting that this is the area hardest hit by the country's shortage of skilled labour, a new study has shown. The study showed that the greatest shortage was that of physiotherapists, with almost 11,600 unfilled vacancies. The shortfall for dental assistants was 7,350, and 7,100 for healthcare and nursing staff, according to the study. (Times of India, 2023).

Aging Population vs. Shrinking Medical Workforce: A Growing Healthcare Crisis

An aging population leads to an increasing demand for healthcare services. This increases the burden on existing skilled labour," according to the authors of the study, carried out by the Competence Centre for Securing Skilled Labour at the German Economic Institute (IW). (Times of India, 2023). Due to the aging of the German population, a growing demand for health and care services is generally expected over the coming years and decades. The number of people in need of care is forecast to rise from the current 2.5 million to 3.5 million by 2030, and even to 4.7 million by 2050 (Federal Statistical Office 2008: 28).

Only then, as a result of population decline, is a slight decline expected (4.6 million for 2060). Particularly high increases in the number of people in need of care are predicted for the federal states of Baden-Württemberg (+316,000), Bavaria (+345,000), and North Rhine-Westphalia (+442,000) by 2050 . (Bonin et al., 2015). The problem has been exacerbated by the increased health demands in an ageing population, with Germany's public health agency, the Robert Koch Institute (RKI), predicting that the percentage of people aged 65 or older will grow from the current 21% to 29% by 2030. (Times of India , 2023) . Germany is grappling with a significant shortage of medical personnel that is likely to be exacerbated by an aging population of doctors and increasing demand for healthcare services. The numbers are deeply troubling, especially in rural areas. Over 36 percent of current general practitioners are over 60 years old, and in the next three years, it is estimated that their imminent retirement will lead to the closure of five to eight thousand doctors' practices. Currently, 85 percent of German doctors are working full-time, down from 98 percent in 2009. 40 percent of healthcare jobs vacated during the COVID-19 pandemic remain unfilled today, and the physicians that remain are spending more of their working time on administrative tasks and less on direct patient care. Of those physicians still working, 35 percent consider themselves likely to leave their role in the next five years. Some respondents hoped to switch careers in favor of jobs in consulting, teaching, or the pharmaceutical and biotech industries . (Protzman , 2025) . There are currently around 55,000 general practitioners in Germany. Now the baby boomers are retiring, and around a third of general practitioners are 60 years or older. According to a study by the Robert Bosch Foundation from May of this year, more than half of general practitioners will retire by 2035. (Peters, 2025) .

Talented young people who want to become doctors can't get a place at university." There are currently 10,500 medical school places available for first-year students in Germany each year; shortly after reunification, there were 16,000. Today, there are four applicants for one place . (Peters , 2025) .

Weak Foundations: How Poor Infrastructure in Medical Education Threatens Healthcare System

The Marburger Bund, representing doctors, advocates for a significant increase in medical school capacities to counteract the impending shortage of physicians as the Baby Boomer generation retires. The MFT has expressed reservations, emphasizing that expanding student numbers too quickly could compromise the quality of medical education. They argue that without adequate resources and infrastructure, a rushed expansion could produce underprepared doctors, ultimately harming patient care. Given the urgency of the situation, there is insufficient time to train a new generation of physicians before the current

workforce diminishes to critical levels. Without immediate action, the risk of a significant shortage becomes increasingly real, jeopardizing healthcare delivery across the nation. Strategic measures are essential to ensure that the medical workforce can be maintained and enhanced considering impending retirements. (Protzman,2025) . Internationally, training for nursing careers is primarily at university level, lasts at least four years, and culminates in a bachelor's or master's degree. Entry is required after at least twelve years of schooling. In Germany, however, training in health and nursing, pediatric nursing, and geriatric nursing takes place at nursing schools or vocational schools. Entry is possible after ten years of schooling, and the training lasts three years full-time. Training at vocational schools includes both theoretical and practical components: at least 2,100 hours of theoretical instruction and around 2,500 hours of practical training. The latter usually takes place in blocks in various fields of work in health and social care facilities. Nursing training in Germany is regulated by two federal laws. This means that nursing training explicitly does not fall under the Vocational Training Act (BBiG), which is why nursing training cannot be described as a dual vocational training program. Nursing is a school-based vocational training program, with sole responsibility resting with the training provider. Therefore, the school is also responsible for the practical part of the training, which takes place in healthcare and care facilities. The training of nursing assistants (healthcare and nursing assistants, as well as geriatric nursing assistants) is regulated exclusively at the state level. Therefore, different regulations apply in each federal state. The training period is one to two years. (Bonin et al., 2015) .

The Vital Role of Migrant Workers in German Healthcare

Immigration might provide a short-term solution, yet it brings its own challenges. The Marburger Bund has opposed tax incentives for foreign specialists for fear of disadvantaging German specialists and expressed concerns about the ethics of recruiting from developing countries that may require their medical professionals' services even more than Germans do. Additionally, bureaucratic hurdles have severely slowed the process of licensing for immigrant doctors; since the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, only about 10 percent of the 1,600 Ukrainian doctors arriving have been fully licensed to practice. To be licensed, foreign doctors must get their credentials translated and pass a medical German language exam before having their foreign-earned medical degree declared equivalent to a German one. Each of Germany's sixteen federal states has its own set of standards. Public perception and acceptance of foreign doctors can also pose barriers. Research indicates that some patients may express reluctance to receive care from foreign-trained physicians, often due to preconceived notions about their capabilities. Recent

studies have shown that many migrant healthcare professionals report experiencing discrimination related to their race and ethnicity. This can lead to reduced job satisfaction among immigrant doctors, potentially resulting in higher turnover rates and further exacerbating the shortage. (Protzman, 2025) . Major challenges include shortages of physicians and medical assistants coupled with geographical mal-allocation, large retirement waves, strong medical hierarchy, weak academisation of nurses, and an expansion of for-profit companies that weaken public control . The PHC workforce is not a policy priority and a systematic strategy for improving recruitment and retention is missing. Policies focus predominantly on physicians with the aim of increasing the recruitment of foreign-trained physicians and making PHC more attractive . PHC interventions are largely physician-centred, including a comprehensive increase in medical training capacity, quotas with prioritised access to medical education for those planning to work in PHC in rural areas, incentives for GP specialisation and PHC providers (shorter education, some recognition of other qualifications). Multi-professional workforce development is lacking, but organisational changes are present seeing an increase in large private PHC centres with multi-professional provider groups supporting skill-mix and team approaches . The WHO PHC model and the SDGs are largely missing from the workforce debate. (Koch K et al., 2011) .

The Impact of Insurance Policies on Medical Working Conditions

The Germany's healthcare system is primarily funded by the public sector, which levies the funding in the form of social insurance payments, and covers in particular the costs of state supervision and basic infrastructure (e.g. administrative bodies and ministries, government institutes and facilities, public health offices and medical education). The premiums collected by the public and private health and nursing insurance companies, on the other hand, are employed for direct healthcare services, such as the remuneration of service providers (e.g. physicians, nurses), the cost of medicine, therapies and medical aids as well as equipment. Private households pay deductibles and healthcare expenses such as over-the-counter medicines and services not covered by health insurance. Healthcare services are provided by both public (e.g. federal, state, and municipal government), non-profit organizations (churches and charities, such as Caritas and the German Red Cross) and private institutions (companies and individuals with commercial interests), with non-profit and private healthcare providers providing the bulk of direct services . Basic principles of social rights are used as the framework for ensuring social security in cases of illness, and must be followed by both the health insurance companies and health

service providers. The principle of the welfare state is based on the Federal Republic of Germany's Basic Law (Grundgesetz), which specifies that the state must guarantee all citizens social justice and the equal participation in society, including appropriate treatment in case of illness. Individuals with below average earning power or economic resources must receive the same quality and quantity of medical care as others. Specifically, the state is obligated according to the Basic Law to provide its citizens with the minimum provisions for a human life with dignity, including adequate medical care that meets the needs of the population (principle of meeting need, Bedarfsdeckungsprinzip), in terms of ambulatory services, inpatient beds, quantitative and qualitative measures, and the dispensing of medical products. This is expressed legally as the service guarantee contract (Sicherstellungsauftrag). However, the federal government does not have to meet this obligation directly, but can delegate the service guarantee contract to state governments and other institutions. While, with the exception of military hospitals, the federal government does not directly fund healthcare facilities, it does maintain a number of healthcare institutes and federal agencies, each with its own areas of responsibility. Döring & Paul, 2012)

Policy Measures

Discuss on : Implementing targeted immigration policies in Germany to attract qualified health care professionals :

The German healthcare sector is already missing health workers and migrant workers can help filling these gaps. General migration policies have been already revised as a reaction to the issue of labour shortages in the economy and opened up improved migration opportunities for health professionals such as doctors and nurses. Access to jobs in the healthcare sector has also been improved, particularly by easing the recognition procedure of foreign qualifications that has been substantially used by migrant health workers. Differences between EU and non-EU citizens have become less pronounced over time but still EU nationals enjoy easier access to the healthcare sector both in terms of migration opportunities and recognition conditions. In line with these legal developments, the number of foreign nationals working in the healthcare sector in Germany has been on the rise, thus showing the sector's absorption capacity for migrant workers. However, despite the increasing relevance in absolute and relative terms, migrant workers are still

underrepresented in the healthcare sector in relation to their share on the total working population. Over time, the sector seems to attract more EU nationals than non-EU national that could be partly explained by the much more favourable regulatory framework for EU migrants. The healthcare sector in Hamburg has also gained in importance for the local economy and shows even a faster job growth than the federal level. Remarkably, in contrast to the federal level, the share of foreign nationals in the healthcare sector in Hamburg stagnated or declined over time. The lower absorption capacity for migrant workers in Hamburg could be to a large extent related to the specific characteristics of the locality such as attractiveness and labour shortages. Furthermore, it could be associated with the integration capacities of the workplace in terms of adaptation and retention . (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p .27) .

Role of foreign workers in the health care sector in Germany

Skilled workers with a migration background are crucial to the German healthcare system Health and social care in Germany, when not carried out by family members, depends to a great extent on people who have either migrated to Germany themselves or who come from families with a history of migration. Over four million people work in the health and social care sector. In 2019, nearly a quarter of these had a migration background. This includes, for example, doctors as well as care staff. Approximately four out of five of all those in paid work in the sector are women. The proportion of those with a migration background is particularly high in geriatric care, where three out of ten workers are migrants or come from migrant families, often from Eastern or south-eastern Europe. The proportion of doctors in Germany with a migration background 1 is also higher than average in relation to the general population; more than a quarter of all practising doctors either migrated to Germany themselves or were born to parents who migrated here. Around 14 per cent are foreign nationals, with the most common countries of origin being Syria and Romania. Compared to their German colleagues, non-German doctors tend to work more often in clinics and in more rural areas. In the federal states in eastern Germany, excluding Berlin, the proportion of non-German doctors is as high as 15 per cent – around three times as high as the proportion of foreign nationals in the general population of those states. At the same time, a number of doctors trained in Germany now practise abroad, for example in Switzerland . (SVR, 2023, pp.. 1 –2) . In recent years, an increasing number of health and social care workers born and trained abroad have moved to Germany. The number of non-German migrants (that is, migrants who were born abroad and do not have German citizenship) working in the healthcare system nearly doubled between 2013 and 2019. In addition, an increasing number of skilled workers in the sector were

born to migrant parents in Germany and have gone through the German education system . ((SVR, 2023, p. 2) . Although state institutions consider migration as a measure with a low potential for dealing with labour shortages , migration plays a crucial role for the labour market both in the short and long run. Migration is almost by default considered a short-term solution to deal with current open vacancies because extended training periods of health professionals particularly doctors impact on the workforce size with a time lag . For demographic reasons, migration is also taken into consideration, when speaking of long-term shortages . In terms of migration policies, Germany has gradually opened up for qualified workers particularly since 2005. Companies are allowed to recruit qualified workers fulfilling minimum requirements in terms of labour conditions and salary arrangements. .(Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p. 10).

The increasing number of migrants in the health care sector in Germany

The number of workers in the healthcare sector increased by 19.6 per cent from 4,115,000 in 2000 to 4,920,000 in 2011 (Federal Statistical Office 2013b) and is still on the rise. In contrast to other economic sectors such as construction or automotive industry, it has shown a high resistance to the economic crisis from 2008 . Besides the trend of a steadily increasing number of workers, the healthcare sector shows a trend of feminization. The share of women rose from 71.9 per cent to 74 per cent from 2000 to 2011 . Whereas doctor's occupations are rather gender balanced, in non-academic occupations such as medical-technical assistants and pharmaceutical management assistants women hold more than 90 per cent of the jobs . Most of the health workers are dependent salaried workers. The biggest groups among self-employed workers in 2012 were doctors with 35 per cent of about 348,700 doctors and pharmacists with 18,172 freelancers . In terms of employment forms, there is a trend towards an increasing relevance of part-time employment. From 2000 to 2010, part-time jobs in the healthcare sector were showing a growth of 70 per cent in contrast to 37 per cent in the overall economy . As a result, one third of the health workers in 2010 had part-time jobs as opposed to a quarter in 2000 . Temporary agency work increasingly takes place and there were 25,045 temporary agency workers in 2011. The health workforce comprises a variety of occupations categorized in four statistical categories: healthcare service occupations (Gesundheitsdienstberufe) that are directly related to the provision of health , social occupations (e.g. elderly care nurses), health crafts persons (e.g. opticians or dental technicians) and other special occupations.²⁶ With 2,793,000 persons, the healthcare service occupations represented 57 per cent of the health workers in 2011 . Among them, the four biggest occupational groups in 2011 were

nursing and midwifery professionals , followed by medical assistants (23.2 per cent), doctors and dentists (14.7 per cent) and nursing assistants (9.8 per cent) (see Figure 3). Over time, medical assistants, nursing professionals and midwifery professionals as well as doctors and dentists have slightly lost relevance in favour of other professions, above all nursing assistants. However, in absolute numbers all these occupations have been growing. The most significant growth by 83 percent is observed in the case of elderly care workers and nursing assistants (32 per cent). The growth in medical assistants and doctors accounted for 17 per cent and 16 per cent .(Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, pp. 18–19).

Policy alternatives

1. Migration policies and Differentiated working Policies for EU and Non-EU Workers :

After the guest worker period in the 1950s and 1960s that ended with the introduction of a recruitment stop in 1973, the German migration policies had been restrictive for a long period of time. Not until 2000s the German migration policies started displaying an increased acceptance of immigration particularly with the new immigration law from 2005 that changed the terminology and the structure of the legal framework . The German regulatory framework that is strongly influenced by EU regulations distinguishes mainly between two categories of migrants: citizens of EU member states and of other non-EU countries. EU nationals benefit from the principle of free movement of workers that provides them with unrestricted access to the German territory and labour market under the same conditions as German nationals. Neither a residence nor a work permit is required in order to take up employment. For newly accepted EU member states, Germany has been traditionally making use of transitional periods in the area of free movement of workers. After the expiration of the transitional rules for the eight Central and Eastern European countries on 1 May 2011 and Bulgaria and Romania on 1 January 2014, currently only citizens from the Croatia are exposed to transitional periods. Croatian nationals need to apply for a work permit with the International Placement Office of the Federal Employment Agency in order to be employed as dependent workers or to provide services in the construction sector and related branches of industry such as cleaning services for buildings and interior decorators. For the healthcare sector, it implies that a Croatian doctor needs a work permit in order to be employed in a German hospital but

he or she can set up an own surgery under the same conditions as a German colleague as the freedom of establishment is not restricted.¹⁴ However, as foreign doctors work predominantly in inpatient facilities and only 13 per cent were self-employed in 2012, their access to the labour market is, nonetheless, affected by the transitional rules. With regard to migration policies targeting third-country nationals, the reluctance to attract migrant workers has gradually decreased. Two changes of particular relevance for migrant health workers from third countries took place in the regulatory framework in the 2000s.

2. The introduction of the Blue Card and attract Highly-Skilled Workers

the introduction of the Blue Card for highly-skilled workers in August 2012 and the so-called Whitelist for skilled workers in July 2013. The Blue Card as a new residence title was introduced in the course of implementation of the EU directive on highly qualified employment. Non-EU nationals with a university degree may be granted a residence permit to take up employment corresponding to their qualification if they can prove a job contract or a job offer and a minimum annual salary of 47,000 euro as set for 2014. To professions with labour shortages such as IT specialists, engineers and doctors, a lower level of annual salary of 37,128 euro applies. The Blue Card is issued by the responsible foreigners' authority for a maximum period of four years and no consent of the Federal Employment Agency is required. After 33 months of employment and payment of contributions to the retirement scheme a person can apply for a permanent residence title. Generally, third-country nationals need to wait 60 months before being entitled to apply. A further improvement of the conditions of entry for third-country nationals with a university degree is the possibility to obtain a visa for six months for the purpose of job seeking. Foreign graduates from German universities are allowed to stay 18 instead of 12 months in order to seek for employment. (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, pp. 10–11).

3. Whitelist and vocational training facilities for medical personal

Non-academics with vocational training from non-EU countries benefit from the legal amendment of the Employment Ordinance (Beschäftigungsverordnung), in force since July 2013. The so-called Whitelist issued by the Federal Employment Agency contains non-academic professions requiring vocational training that face labour shortages. In the Whitelist in 2014 the following health occupations are included: health and nursing professions without specialisation, specialist nursing professions, elderly care professions, and surgical technology/medical technical assistance professions. The access

to the German labour market for the listed professions is less regulated as the consent of the Federal Employment Agency is needed but the so-called priority check (Vorrangprüfung) is not required. Although it is not checked whether the employment of a German or an EU worker is possible, a priority check is indirectly done as the prerequisite for filling a vacancy with a foreigner is that the position has been published in the job exchange portal of the Federal Employment Agency for a sufficient period of time . It is important to note that the education required for a certain occupation depends on the German regulations and not on those of the country of origin. Correspondingly, to a nurse with a tertiary education who wants to immigrate to Germany the Whitelist instead of the Blue Card regulation applies. Apart from labour migration regulations such as the Blue Card and Whitelist, migrant workers may use other migration channels provided by the law such as migration in the framework of family reunification or university education and vocational training. Moreover, the requirements for a residence permit for self-employment – investment of at least one million euros or the creation of at least ten jobs – do not apply to doctors who want to set up an own surgery in case of a potential special regional need for medical care . With regard to recruitment of health workers from abroad, Germany is geared to the Global Code of Practice on the International Recruitment of Health Personnel of the World Health Organisation adopted in May 2010. On the one hand it recommends to industrial countries to abstain from recruiting health workers from developing countries hit by severe labour shortages. On the other hand it is emphasised that the right of skilled workers of mobility should not be constrained. Germany among other countries decided to dissolve this contradiction by sticking to a list of 57 developing countries defined as facing critical shortages . In November 2013, a ban on recruitment and placement of health professionals from the identified countries was added to the Employment Ordinance. For that reason, the recruitment of migrant workers in nursing and care occupations from these countries may be undertaken only by the Federal Employment Agency . In the past, Germany had actively recruited nurses and care workers in the framework of bilateral agreements: in the 1960s and 1970s with South Korea, Philippines and India , in the 1980s and the 1990s with Yugoslavia , and since 2005 with eight European countries: Croatia, Ukraine, Poland, Slovenia, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic, Bulgaria and Romania (Dhillon et al. 2010). The last bilateral agreement in force, that with Croatia, expired in 2012 . Active recruitment of doctors abroad did not take place for more than 30 years . The presence of foreign doctors in the German healthcare sector can be thus attributed to the integration of foreign students or refugees but not to active recruitment of migrant health professionals . (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, pp . 12–13) .

4. The website www.make-it-in-germany.com launched to attract migrant workers

For the first time since 1973, national and local initiatives for active recruitment abroad were launched. The website www.make-it-in-germany.com launched in 2012 aims at attracting international workers particularly from shortage occupations by providing them with useful information about migration and economic opportunities in Germany, and presenting Germany as an attractive place to work and live.¹⁵ Active recruitment strategies are implemented by state institutions. The International Placement Office of the Federal Employment Agency (Zentrale Ausland – und Fachvermittlung, ZAV) supports German companies in the recruitment process abroad by cooperating with national authorities of the sending countries and organizing events such as European Job Days and job exchanges with the EURES network (European Employment Services). In addition to mechanical engineering and technology, and hotel and catering industry, the healthcare sector is one of three sectors the Central Placement Office is focusing on.¹⁶ The role of recruitment agencies is minor. Pilot projects for international recruitment in the healthcare sector were launched with both EU and nonEU countries. In the EU, activities for attracting migrant health workers take place mainly in four member states with high potential for job seekers: Greece, Italy, Portugal and Spain. In 2013, a special programme MobiPro-EU was launched with the aim at attracting young people from EU member states to do vocational training in occupations with labour shortages, long-term care work being one of them. With regard to recruitment from non-EU countries, in 2013, the Central Placement Office of the Federal Employment Agency entered into an agreement about placement of nurses with the respective employment agencies of Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Philippines and possibly Tunisia. The recruitment in the framework of the so-called Triple-Win-Project is supported by the Federal Agency for International Cooperation (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit, GIZ) that is responsible for the linguistic and professional preparation and accompanying integration activities of about 2,000 qualified nurses in German companies. Furthermore, pilot programmes with China for recruitment of 150 Chinese elderly care nurses and with Vietnam for the training of 100 geriatric nurses in Germany were launched. These pilot programmes aim at reducing labour shortages in Germany but also at gathering experience with appropriate recruitment of migrant health workers, so that well managed migration has a positive impact on both sending and receiving countries. (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p.13).

In spite of the improvements of the regulatory framework for highly-qualified third-country nationals and Germany being one of the countries with the lowest barriers for highly skilled migration, labour migration to Germany remains at a

low level. Migration of health workers other than doctors to Germany is minimal . No statistical data on foreign doctors and nurses migrating to Germany are collected. According to calculations based on Microcensus data, 35,900 foreign-trained doctors were pursuing their profession in 2010 and 32,800 foreign doctors obtained their qualification in Germany . Thus nearly 20 per cent out of 373,000 doctors working in 2010 in Germany were migrants. .(Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p.14) .

5. Federal Legislation on Training Healthcare Workers: Policies and Implementation

With regard to access of migrant workers to the German healthcare sector, it has to be distinguished between two main ways: directly after training in the field of health in Germany or after an admission to practice the profession of foreign-trained workers. The Federal Statistical Office provides data on education of foreign nationals at health vocational schools and universities. Statistics on health vocational schools show that 6.7 per cent of about 135,000 pupils in 2012 had a foreign nationality . The share of foreign nationals in health studies at universities amounted to 9 per cent in 2012. In spite of the increase in the period 2000-2012, foreign nationals are still underrepresented in health fields of study compared to their share in all fields of study (11.3 per cent in 2012) . Interestingly, foreign nationals are overrepresented in human medicine, amounting to 17 per cent of all students. It is important to note that the increased share of foreign students cannot be certainly attributed to increased migration for educational purposes as there are many foreign nationals who obtained secondary education in Germany (so-called Bildungsinländer) and are not considered educational migrant. With regard to foreign nationals who obtained training in health abroad, it has to be distinguished between migrant health workers that come to Germany to obtain further qualification and those that intend to pursue their profession. The former needs an academic recognition whereas the latter recognition of professional qualification . Doctors who intend to do specialty training in a German hospital thus need an academic recognition by a university whereas those who want to work in hospital need recognition of their professional qualification by the respective institutions in charge. In the latter case, it is important whether the professional qualification is regulated or non-regulated. Regulated professions such as doctors, pharmacists, nurses and care workers require the approval by German authorities whereas non-regulated professions such as medical receptionists can be practised without an official admission. Migrant health workers in regulated professions need to prove (a) equivalent qualifications referring to the German standard and (b) sufficient German language skills. .(Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p.14) .

6. Federal laws regarding the recognition for foreign qualification

As most of the health professions are regulated, the recognition of foreign qualifications is a crucial prerequisite for accessing the German healthcare sector. To draw a more detailed picture of the prevalent access regulations, a closer look is taken at two main health professions, doctors and nurses. Doctors in Germany need a full licence to practise in order to pursue their profession (Approbation). The Federal Medical Regulation distinguishes between two types of licence to practise differing in terms of duration and entitlements: full (Approbation) and provisional (Berufserlaubnis) in accordance with 10 of the Federal Medical Regulation. Whereas the full licence is valid across Germany for an unlimited period of time and allows both dependent work and selfemployment, the provisional licence is issued for a period up to two years and for an individual state (Land), and the setting up of an own surgery is not allowed. German graduates obtain a full licence to practise after graduation. In the past, foreign-trained doctors from EU member states, Australia, Israel, Japan, Canada and New Zealand were entitled to a full licence, because their medical degrees were considered equivalent to the German degree. Foreign nationals from the rest of the third countries were not entitled to a full licence and might obtain only a provisional licence even if they graduated from a German university. The current legal framework does not distinguish between nationalities and countries of origin anymore that is a major improvement related to the access of foreign nationals from third countries to the sector. According to the Recognition Law, all persons irrespective of their residence status and citizenship are entitled to start a procedure for a full licence.¹⁷ A provisional licence is still issued in case of a temporary professional practice in Germany and does not encompass recognition of professional qualifications by the issuing authority. (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p.15).

Discussion

What is driving the labour shortage in healthcare?

Demand for doctors is a pressing issue. A study from the government-backed Competence Centre for Skilled Workers, showed that around 47,000 positions in the healthcare sector, ranging from physiotherapists to dental assistants, were unfilled in the 12-month period between July 2023 and June 2024.

Germany's healthcare sector is experiencing a twin pinch of low numbers of medical graduates entering the profession, and high numbers of doctors reaching retirement age. Compared to neighbouring EU countries, Germany has one of the lowest rates of medics graduating with 12.4 graduates per 100,000 inhabitants in 2022. Adding to the pressure of fewer graduates is the ageing workforce. Germany had Europe's highest share of physicians aged 55–64 years at 36.1% in 2022. The ageing population is also placing increased demands on already strained healthcare services. The number of people aged 65 and older is projected to almost double, from 16 million to an estimated 24 million by 2040, according to Germany's statistical office. Skilled migrant workers are crucial to keeping the health service running in future, according to a 2023 report from the Expert Council on Integration and Migration, a Berlin-based research body. (Gill, 2025) .

How many foreign-born doctors are working in Germany?

Foreign medics make up about 14% of the healthcare workforce, according to a 2023 report from the German Medical Association. The number of foreign-born doctors reached a new high in 2023 at almost 64,000, double the 30,000 registered in 2013. Thirty years ago, there were around 10,000 foreign doctors working in Germany, according to the German Medical Association. Around 10,000 Syrians work in German hospitals, making them the largest group of foreign doctors in the country, according to the Syrian Society for Doctors and Pharmacists in Germany. Former chancellor Angela Merkel's decision in 2015 to welcome over one million asylum seekers, predominantly from Syria, was controversial in Germany, while some political analysts have blamed it for contributing to the rise of the AfD. After the fall of the then Syrian president Bashar al-Assad last December, some German politicians suggested it was time for Germany's Syrian refugees to consider returning home. However, the chairman of the German Hospital Federation (DKG) said that if large numbers of Syrians left, they would leave "noticeable gaps" in the provision of care, although he said the service wouldn't collapse. (Gill, 2025) .

Germany, under its Social Democrat chancellor Olaf Scholz, reintroduced immigration checks at all its land borders last September, a move that drew criticism from neighbouring countries which said it breached the European Union's principle of free movement.

The move was in response to public concerns amid a spate of violent incidents involving people with an immigrant background, which has stoked support for the far-right AfD party, and led some other politicians to toughen their stance on migration. These incidents included a car-ramming and deadly knife attack. Leading in the latest polls, the opposition Christian Democratic Union (CDU) and the AfD have called for a stronger crackdown on migration policy,

including permanent border controls, increased detentions of "illegal immigrants", outsourcing asylum processes to non-EU countries and resuming deportations to Syria and Afghanistan.

Two-thirds of the German public support stronger immigration rules, a recent poll showed. But another poll showed that voters' main concerns included the economy and high prices . (Gill, 2025, paras. 1 –4) .

So how is Germany responding?

Germany has relaxed some rules to attract skilled foreign workers. It introduced the Skilled Workers Immigration Act in 2020 and expanded the law in 2023 with the aim of broadening access to the labour market for non-EU nationals, in many cases by simplifying and fast-tracking visa applications. However, the centre-right CDU, whose leader Friedrich Merz is widely tipped to become the next chancellor, and far-right AfD party opposed the 2023 law, arguing that the law's definition of skilled labour was too broad. Germany has signed or is in the process of signing migration partnerships with 10 countries, including Kenya, India and the Philippines, to allow skilled workers from these countries to live and work in Europe's largest economy. (Gill, 2025) .

Educational and career paths

Education in the field of healthcare can be obtained in three types of training facilities: in the so-called dual educational system, in vocational schools and at universities and universities of applied sciences (Eckert 2011b). The dual educational system combining apprenticeship in a health facility and vocational education in a school is decentralized and training capacities depend on the offer of training positions by the employers. In the dual system mainly medical and dental assistants are trained. Nurses and care workers are predominantly trained in vocational schools. Although in recent years university education of nursing professionals is possible, nursing in Germany is still a non-academic profession. As academic professionals, doctors and dentists are trained at universities. As there are more applicants than the university system can accept, 20 percent of the study places are awarded by the principle *numerus clausus*, 20 percent by waiting periods for the medical study and 40 percent by the universities' selection procedures, confining the access to education to the best applicants.⁸ The most training positions in the healthcare sector are in vocational and professional schools – 207,000 in 2006/2007 – compared to 89,000 in the dual system and a comparable number of enrolled students at universities . (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p. 3).

Different career paths are typical for the health occupations of interest for this report – doctors and nurses. Enrollment in human medicine at a university is possible after completed 12 years of secondary education (Abitur). After six

years of university education and final exams graduates obtain a licence to practise as generalists (Approbation). Graduated generalists can practice as employees in hospitals, health centers or medical practices but are not allowed to set up an own practice, for which a further specialty training is required. A specialty can be obtained in each health facility that possesses an authorisation to offer specialty training by the Chamber of Physicians . hospital being main providers of specialty training. Doctors in specialty training are mostly employed as assistant doctors and can become a medical specialist after at least five years of training on the job and an exam with the respective State Chamber of Physicians After specialty training, doctors can further work as an employee or set up an own medical practice as a self-employed doctor. Doctors in medical practices provide ambulant services and work under contract to the statutory health insurance funds or treat privately insured patients. Depending on the specialty training, self-employed doctors work as a general practitioner (which is a specialty field in Germany as well) or as a specialist doctor. Patients are encouraged to visit a general practitioner first, who refers to specialists or a hospital when necessary. Doctors in hospitals which are responsible for emergency cases and long-term care are salaried specialists and provide inpatient services. In terms of remuneration, doctors are ranked on the top of the payment scale for academic professions in Germany . Fee-for-service is the predominant mode of payments for general physicians and specialists working in ambulatory care. Doctors employed in inpatient institutions (mainly hospitals) receive salaries dependent on their career level and working experience . Comparing the average salary of medical specialists in Germany with that of their counterparts in OECD countries, German specialist doctors are midrange . (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p. 4).

Nursing education takes places in a vocational school. Ten years of schooling is required in order to take up training in nursing. Training as general or pediatric nurses takes three years and ends with a state examination whereas nursing assistants undergo one year of training. Further two-year specialty training is necessary to become a nursing specialist such as a surgical nurse or a cardiac nurse. University education is either possible after accomplished vocational training or after four year relevant working experience and is generally part of the further qualification of a nurse. Since 2003, primary nursing training at university is offered (Wissenschaftsrat 2012). However, the number of academic training opportunities for nursing directly related to patients' care remains low. 21,000 places in vocational schools and only 600 university places are provided annually . Further reforms of educational paths of nursing are model tests for a generalised vocational training with the aim at merging the three branches of nursing: general nurses, pediatric nurse and elderly care nurse into one general nursing training . Nurses are employed predominantly in

hospitals, clinics and practices of specialized doctors and rarely in practices of general practitioners where medical assistants are employed. The general core tasks of a nurse are the provision of care to patients, assistance to the doctor's treatment and documentation. Nursing assistants support nursing professionals in the field of hygiene, documentation and therapeutic measures. (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p.) .

Shortages are partly related to a mismatch of provided and requested specialist doctors (Finotelli 2014) that could be explained with the systematic training of young doctors in special fields by hospitals. This is reflected in the number of office-based specialists that increased more rapidly than the number of general practitioners, which dropped to less than 30 per cent of all office-based doctors in 2012 . Labour shortages affect German regions differently. Thus less attractive rural areas face a significant lack of general practitioners . The attractiveness of the German healthcare system also plays a role. German health professionals are in search for adequate payment and better working conditions, with less bureaucracy, less hierarchy and more flexible working hours . This could lead to emigration of health professionals towards more attractive countries. The number of doctors leaving Germany annually in the period 2008-2012 ranged between 2,500 and 3,500, with two-thirds of them being German nationals . The most preferred destinations were Switzerland, Austria, the US and the UK. According to estimates, about 17,000 German doctors were working in foreign countries in 2010 and the number of doctors leaving Germany for work abroad is increasing . Apart from emigration, shortages may have led to a vicious circle in some fields. Bottlenecks may lead to increasing workload in the workplace which may lead to increasing drop-outs of personnel and in turn result in shortages. (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p. 8–9).

Policy measures

Migrant workers by occupation and facility

Data on employees subject to social security contribution give insight into the presence of foreign nationals in individual occupations. The biggest occupational groups in 2011 were nursing professionals and midwives (35 per cent) and medical receptionists (26 per cent), followed by nursing assistants (13 per cent) and doctors (9 percent). The number of workers in all those occupations increased from 2008 to 2011. As Figure 4 shows, the growth rates for foreign nationals were higher than for German nationals. In the period 2008-2011, the number of employees increased by 22.8 per cent for EU nationals and

by 19.4 per cent for non-EU nationals, as opposed to only 7.7 per cent for German nationals. Interestingly, the greatest increase is observed in the case of doctors particularly for EU nationals that more than doubled (58.4 per cent) and non-EU nationals that increased by more than a third (36.6 per cent) . (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p. 22) .

1. Visa Policies and Their Impact on Migrant Health Professionals

Besides Microcensus and labour statistics, data on doctors by nationality is available. Doctors in Germany have to register with the respective State Chambers of Physicians and these administrative data are published annually by the German Medical Association. It is more inclusive compared to data of the Federal Employment Agency as it encompasses not only persons subject to social security contributions but also self-employed persons and civil servants. Data by nationality are available but it is not possible to differentiate between foreign nationals with foreign training and with training in Germany. Indications about inflow of foreign doctors are given by data on new registrations of doctors from EU member states although registration is probably not occurring in the year of migration. The number of EU doctors who accessed the German healthcare sector for the first time increased from 226 in 2000 to 2,225 in 2012 with a particular growth since the EU enlargements in 2004 and 2007. Main nationalities in 2012 were Romania, Greece, Hungary, Austria and Bulgaria. Since 2000, the number of registered doctors with a foreign nationality has been steadily increasing and rose by 75 per cent from 14,600 in 2000 to almost 32,600 in 2012 . The vast majority of foreign doctors were registered in the former Western states. In 2012 two-thirds of the foreign doctors were registered in four states: North Rhine-Westphalia, Bavaria, BadenWürttemberg and Lower Saxony. Hamburg as a city state made up only 2 per cent of all foreign doctors. More than half of the foreign doctors in Germany come from an EU member state, followed by Asia (18 per cent) and other European countries (17 per cent). Main nationalities in 2012 were Romania, Greece, Austria, Russia and Poland. Main third countries were Russia, Iran, Syria, Turkey and Ukraine. Over time, the relevance of EU as a sending region increased from 41 per cent in 2005 to 56 per cent in 2012 whereas the rest of Europe displayed a decline from 29 per cent to 17 per cent . Data collected by the State Chamber of Physicians in Hamburg showed that the number of foreign doctors registered in Hamburg rose from 429 to 659 in the period 2005-2013 . This is in line with the increasing number of doctors in Hamburg. However, compared to the federal level, the growth of registered foreign doctors in Hamburg is less considerable. Both the number of EU and non-EU doctors increased but the growth of registrations by EU nationals is more pronounced (111 per cent) than those by non-EU nationals

(22 per cent). The increased relevance of doctors from EU countries could be explained by the EU enlargements and the transition of important sending countries from third countries to EU member states. The share of EU nationals increased from 35 per cent to 48 per cent, resulting in rather balanced shares of EU and non-EU regions in 2013. Foreign doctors came mainly from Austria, Greece, Iran, Turkey, Poland and Russia . .(Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015, p.25) .

2. Policy measures regarding the Recognition process for foreign qualification

Fast-track the recognition of foreign qualifications and simplify compensation measures In response to a significant shortage of skilled workers, legislation has been put in place in recent years to make it easier for qualified foreign nationals to immigrate to Germany. Skilled workers are especially needed in the health and social care sector. However, to work legally in Germany they must prove that their qualifications meet German standards; if this is not the case, they are required to obtain additional training in Germany to enable full recognition. The success of any recruitment strategy aimed at attracting skilled workers from abroad therefore depends on how such recognition procedures are implemented in practice. Overall, the federal states (Länder) are responsible for recognition procedures. To bring about greater efficiency and transparency, the states need to make their procedures simpler and bring them into alignment, while also ensuring that the relevant authorities work in a more 2 joined-up way. Further, the authorities involved in the migration process – such as German consular services abroad, immigration offices, government bodies responsible for assessing foreign qualifications and the Federal Employment Agency – must improve how they work together. Migration must be understood as a holistic process in which each individual step is dependent for its success on all the others. The SVR also recommends pooling competences in each federal state and making full use of the opportunities offered by a more digitalised administration. To build expertise and accelerate the recognition process, it could be useful to assign responsibility for specific countries of origin or occupations to specific federal states. The relevant authorities also need significantly more staff in order to process applications more quickly . (SVR, 2023, pp. 27– 28) .

3. Empowering the Workforce: Enhancing Training Opportunities for Migrant Workers

Where applicants need further training in order to gain full recognition, it is important to ensure that they can complete such training as soon as possible. The SVR therefore recommends expanding compensation measures (as this additional training is known) on a modular basis while ensuring better

coordination of existing offers not only within each federal state but also between neighbouring states. Courses should always include an element of (specialist) language training; language skills are essential, not only to guarantee the success of the training itself, but also to ensure that the applicant can carry out their profession successfully in Germany and to facilitate integration into their workplace. In addition, capacity for providing the necessary knowledge or aptitude test to prove that an applicant meets the recognition requirements should be increased to the point where applicants can take the relevant test within six months. (SVR, 2023, p.3) . Encourage migration for educational purposes and improve education and training in Germany Along with recruiting (qualified) health and social care workers, the SVR also recommends stepping up recruitment abroad for training in Germany. Migrants who complete the whole of their training in Germany avoid lengthy recognition procedures, while the contact to other students facilitates language learning and social integration. This would also avoid potential transfer problems that can arise where the job profile and training differ substantially between the country of origin and the target country. This, in turn, facilitates workplace integration. Recruiting students, rather than fully qualified professionals, also helps to avoid the ‘brain drain’ effect in the students’ country of origin. However, for such a measure to be successful, it is important that potential students have all the relevant information before making a decision. They need to know what they will learn and to understand what their chosen profession is likely to entail, as well as what it is like to live and work in Germany. This is essential in order to manage expectations and develop a realistic picture of what their future in Germany might look like. To address the skills shortage in health and social care in the long term, the SVR also recommends that policy-makers turn their attention to Germany as well as abroad. It is important to consider recruitment strategies for people who already live here. Besides schoolleavers, these might also be migrants who have not yet completed any vocational training or whose qualification and/or work experience in their country of origin has not yet been recognised. Staff working at assistant level or who are training to become health and social care assistants should be encouraged to go on to train as skilled workers. To reduce the current high drop-out rate for students in the sector, especially among those training as care workers, it is also essential that working conditions in the health and social care sector are fundamentally improved . (SVR, 2023, pp. 3 –4) .

The SVR also recommends pooling competences in each federal state and making full use of the opportunities offered by a more digitalised administration. Migrants must be able to complete the required compensation measures without unnecessary delays. For this to happen, module-based courses must be expanded in combination with a greater emphasis on (specialist)

language training, while recruitment processes should be made as transparent as possible. “This means that potential recruits to the sector must be provided with comprehensive information before they apply. They also need support in dealing with the authorities, as well as support from their employer,” explains Professor Thym. In this sector, it is especially important that recruitment abroad does not impact negatively on healthcare in the relevant countries of origin. “Bilateral agreements could ensure that both sides benefit from this form of migration. We see skills partnerships that promote capacity-building in the country of origin, as well as the destination country, as particularly valuable,” says SVR Chairperson Petra Bendel . Promote migration for educational purposes and pay greater attention to integration in the workplace; To address the skills shortage in the healthcare system in the long term, the SVR recommends stepping up recruitment abroad for training in Germany. “This has many advantages. It means that fully-trained workers are not recruited away from their country of origin, while migrants who do the whole of their training in Germany avoid lengthy recognition procedures. This can also avoid the transfer problems that can arise with different job profiles and training, while contact to other students makes it easier for foreign students to learn German. This, in turn, facilitates social integration, and thus also integration in the workplace. After all, we don’t just want to attract skilled workers from abroad – we also want them to stay once they’ve arrived,” explains Professor Bendel. Health and social care providers recruiting staff from abroad should develop an integration concept and identify staff members who can support the newly-arrived workers. To retain skilled workers over time, the SVR believes it is essential to improve working conditions in the health and social care sector, particularly in social care. “Migration alone cannot solve the structural shortage of skilled workers in this area,” notes Professor Bendel. “We must do more to explore the potential we have here at home in order to attract more people to train for health and social care work – including people who have migrated to Germany themselves or who come from families with a history of migration. But for this to happen, working conditions must improve. We also need a healthcare system that is more responsive to diversity. This would benefit everyone in Germany.” (Expert Council on Integration and Migration(SVR), 2022, paras. 4–6) .

4. Measures regarding to Improve Working Conditions for migrants

Retain skilled workers: encourage workplace integration, improve working conditions Skilled workers recruited from abroad have to work hard to adapt their knowledge and professional experience to their new working environment. To enable them to fulfil the expectations and requirements of their new role, and

to encourage them to want to stay in Germany long-term, they need appropriate support, especially during the initial period when they are ‘learning the ropes’. Not only language can be a challenge, but also often different ways of working and a different understanding of what the role entails. If health and social care providers want to recruit staff from abroad, it is in their own interest that they should prepare adequately for their arrival, develop an integration concept and identify staff members⁴ who can support the newly-arrived workers. Existing staff must be involved in the process from early on. The induction process takes time and initially creates more work for those training the new recruits. This means that it is important to have enough personnel available to undertake this work. Encouraging language competence is particularly important. Working with patients and in multi-professional teams requires excellent communication skills. Organisations should already start planning in enough time for thorough, sector-relevant language training during the recruitment phase. A professional induction should go hand-in-hand with support to assist the integration of the new staff and their families. New recruits need information and advice on a wide range of subjects, from how to find accommodation, childcare and potentially employment for accompanying family members, to information about the local infrastructure, for example public transport. To help develop such support for skilled workers and their families, health and social care providers could work together with local organisations and local authorities. This is especially important in structurally weak regions. To retain skilled workers in the long term, the SVR also believes it is essential to improve working conditions in the health and social care sector, particularly in social care. Migration alone cannot solve the structural shortage of skilled workers in this area. (SVR, 2023, pp. 4–5) Make health worker migration fair and transparent Migration in the health sector is not just a German or European phenomenon. Across all OECD countries, around one quarter of all doctors and one sixth of nurses were not born in the country where they now work. Mobile professionals can often achieve a higher salary abroad than they can at home, and can also enjoy better working conditions or career perspectives. Meanwhile, their countries of origin can profit from remittances, or, in the case of returning migrants, from the skills and knowledge they have gained abroad. But there can also be disadvantages; when healthcare professionals emigrate, this can affect the availability of healthcare and thus the general living standards in their country of origin. To help prevent this negative impact, skilled healthcare workers should be actively recruited only in countries where there is a surplus. Bilateral agreements could ensure that both sides benefit from this form of migration. Skills partnerships that promote capacity-building in the country of origin as well as the destination country are particularly valuable. Bilateral agreements of the kind described above can also minimise the risks associated with migration for skilled workers

if the latter are comprehensively informed about their rights and obligations and, for example, the agreements clarify which costs are borne by the destination country or future employer. Skilled workers already come to Germany via government schemes. Most, however, are recruited directly by companies, come via private brokerage agencies or organise their travel to Germany independently. But these options carry risks – for example, businesses or workers may be unlucky enough to encounter disreputable agencies. The seal of quality ‘Faire Anwerbung Pflege Deutschland’ (‘Fair Recruitment for Care in Germany’) is a government initiative aiming to increase transparency in recruitment in the sector. The SVR therefore recommends that it should be subject to an evaluation process. The SVR believes it is essential to guarantee the greatest possible transparency in healthcare recruitment, ensure that new recruits are provided with comprehensive information in advance and support them in dealing with the authorities . (SVR, 2023, pp. 5–6) .

5. policy Measures regarding to the Integration specially learning the German language

Ensure that live-in care provided by foreign nationals is carried out legally and fairly Many older people would like to spend their last years in their own home, even if they are no longer capable of managing everyday tasks independently. The live-in care model (often marketed, misleadingly, as ‘24-hour care’) offers a chance for them to do so. Care workers – who mostly come from Eastern Europe – live in the person's home and support them in their everyday lives. This model can have advantages, both for the person who requires care and their family. It makes care more affordable, and it means that family members who work are more able to fit in supporting their relatives around their other commitments. For the care workers, it offers a form of labour migration that usually does not require any particular qualifications or language skills. However, this kind of employment often operates in a legal grey area; frequently, employers fail to comply with the relevant legislation, especially when it comes to working hours and paying the minimum wage. The SVR therefore recommends ensuring that all those involved are systematically provided with information about their legal rights and obligations. To protect care workers from overworking and exploitation, and to manage the expectations of the person in need of care and their family, a clear job description is vital. Further, there should be no agreements that result in a single individual providing ‘24-hour care’; this is illegal under German law. Rather, care workers should only be employed where the need for support in everyday life is moderate, or to complement other forms of care provision – for example, as part of a multi-disciplinary support package involving outpatient services and/or community care, care by family members and other forms of support.

Should the person require care for significantly more than 40 hours per week, two or three care workers could be employed in parallel who would be responsible for dividing up the work between themselves. However, employing such a team of workers legally and on fair pay is an option that would only be available to well-off families. (SVR, 2023, pp. 6–7).

6. Policies regarding the Simplifying Migration Process

Migrants generally have good legal access to healthcare provision, but there are gaps. Most people who live without a German passport in Germany today are properly insured in case of illness. However, access to publicly-funded healthcare and to the health insurance system is legally restricted for certain groups: those whose asylum applications have not yet been decided or with an obligation to leave the country, who in addition have been in Germany for less than eighteen months, as well as anyone who is living illegally in Germany. In exceptional cases, these legal restrictions also apply to EU residents who have lost their right to free movement. The overall proportion of persons officially recorded as uninsured in Germany is less than 0.1 per cent of the population. Among those with a migration background it is just under 0.2 per cent and among those without a German passport just under 0.3 per cent. Most people, 8 whether or not they have a migration background, are members of a statutory health insurance scheme. Where migrants in Germany are not adequately insured in case of illness, this is usually not because they do not have a legal right to insurance or because of flawed legislation. Instead, those affected are often not in a position to overcome the various bureaucratic hurdles on their own, either, for example, because of their circumstances and/or because the rules that apply to them are (perceived to be) too complicated. To address this situation requires targeted advice and support that is easily available to all, with as few barriers as possible to accessing it. This would be an important foundation for a health system that is responsive to diversity. The SVR therefore believes that the federal states and local authorities should consider expanding the availability of advice and support centres to help people clarify their rights to medical services and/or access health insurance options ('Clearingstellen'). The situation for migrants without a legal residence status in Germany is especially precarious. Although the provisions of the Asylum Seeker Benefits Act give them the right to healthcare, the legal situation also means that in practice they cannot access such care without risking deportation. The SVR therefore recommends that Article 87.1 of the Residence Act should be amended to clarify that the healthcare sector (including but not limited to emergency care) is exempt from the duty of public bodies to pass on information about undocumented migrants to the immigration authorities. The rules and procedures for means testing in relation to reimbursements from the social

welfare offices should also be developed and aligned across all federal states. (SVR, 2023, pp. 8–9) .

A well-functioning healthcare system is essential for a well-functioning society. In its 2022 Annual Report, the Expert Council on Integration and Migration (SVR) concludes that migrants are crucial to the German healthcare system. To ensure that healthcare is equally available to all, irrespective of background or migration history, the sector as a whole must become more responsive to diversity. Berlin, 13 May 2022. Skilled workers with a migration background are crucial to the German healthcare system. Already today, one in six people working in health and social care was born abroad, while over a quarter of all practising doctors has a migration background – a trend that is set to continue. “Migrants work at all levels of the healthcare system, whether as doctors, carers for the elderly or as nurses. Without migrants, the German healthcare system would collapse – and if we didn’t know this before, the coronavirus pandemic has proved it beyond a doubt,” says Chairperson of the SVR, Professor Petra Bendel. “In view of the ongoing demographic change in German society, the need for skilled workers in the sector will only continue to grow. This means it is essential to ensure that access for those wishing to work in the sector is simplified and improved in a way that is sustainable in the long term. Accelerate procedures for recognising qualifications; simplify compensation measures; make recruitment fair . Skilled workers from abroad who want to work in a regulated profession in Germany must show that their qualifications meet German standards. “Migrants must provide proof of equivalence if they wish to work here. When it comes to health and social care, this is of immense importance to ensure patient safety,” says Professor Daniel Thym, Deputy Chairperson of the SVR. “The success of any recruitment strategy aimed at attracting skilled workers from abroad therefore depends on how recognition procedures are implemented in practice. Migration must be understood as a holistic process in which each individual step is dependent for its success on all the others. We believe that the procedures could be significantly improved. Currently, they are often lengthy, and for migrants going through the process, it is difficult to understand who is responsible for what. Accelerating and simplifying processes further, along with ensuring that they are better aligned, is essential. The authorities involved – such as German consular services abroad, immigration and recognition authorities and the Federal Employment Agency – must improve how they work together,” Thym argues. (Expert Council on Integration and Migration (SVR), 2022, paras. 1–3) .

Policy recommendation

1. Measure regarding to the employment of a new worker and amendments in the working conditions, e.g. wage classification, has to be approved by the works council.

According to managers and works council' representatives, recruitment of migrant workers takes place mostly through initiative applications or general job advertisements. Managers emphasised repeatedly the current labour situation in the healthcare sector in Hamburg as good from an employer's point of view and stressed this as an explanation for the lack of structured concepts for international recruitment in the hospitals. Works councils' representatives also pointed out that the hospitals are at the very beginning of approaching the topic of international recruitment.

Administrative formalities such as residence and work permit and recognition of qualifications hamper the employment of migrant workers, for instance. A HR manager openly admitted that he would prefer a worker who could be easily employed: "They [migrant workers] are often confronted with the problem that they have to pass a complex procedure concerning the residence permit as well as the recognition of their training. If you are not operating coordinately, it is extremely burdensome and difficult. [...] That is why I am glad that we do it very very seldom. First of all, we have enough applications in the field of doctors. That is why we take the easy ones and the ones that know the German language." (MAN7) Beside the burden of formal recognition of qualifications, a manager pointed to difficulties to assess the skills of someone who had worked in another healthcare system and had gathered experiences abroad, for example, in the case of different working culture (MAN5). In order to assess an applicant, it is seen as an advantage to get to know the applicant personally:

2. Measures regarding a general support, particularly related to opportunities for family reunification and labour market participation of family members, is needed

Besides these group-related measures, individual support is provided on a case-by-case basis, for instance, covering costs for language courses or assistance in the search for housing. Given the tense situation at the housing market in Hamburg, support in the search for housing is useful, as both managers and representatives of the works councils emphasised (MAN7, CON4). But also more general support, particularly related to opportunities for family reunification and labour market participation of family members, is needed. In

this regard, the website Dual Career Network Germany used frequently by guest researchers is given as a good example for a supportive measure

3. Measures regarding to the Language and further education for migrant workers

The first project launched in 2012 was a shortened vocational training for nurses whose foreign qualifications were not or were only partly recognised.²⁴ With the aim of preparing them for the recognition examination, a shortened vocational training was organised at the education academy of the university hospital. It lasted 22 months in contrast to the standard vocational training as general nurse of 36 months. The main difficulties in the project were limited language skills of the participants (MAN4). 25 participants attended the course, mainly women and persons from non-EU countries, but a mere eight out of 20 participants passed the final examination. A manager involved in the project stated the main reason in her view: “They had to face the requirements of the nursing exam. There the gap became visible again: They did not understand enough spoken language.” (MAN4) The second project initiated in 2013 was a long-term internship at the education academy of the university hospital. It constituted a compensation measure for foreign-trained nurses whose qualifications were not recognised. It was a one-year course with six separate modules with the aim of obtaining a recognised qualification in nursing. Two courses with six participants per course took place in the hospital. A manager involved in the project addressed the challenges faced:

4. Measures combat racism and xenophobia

Apart from individual support measures, works councils provide more generally support to employees in the workplace. They represent the interest of employees and have co-determination rights related to employment of workers and general working conditions, and provide support to employees in case of conflicts with the employer or in the team. One of the main tasks of works councils are to promote the integration of foreign workers and the further understanding between them and their German colleagues, as well to request activities to combat racism and xenophobia.²⁵ Works councils usually react to problems concerning the integration of migrant workers but seldom act proactively. They took action only in few cases of discrimination because of migration background.

5. Measures regarding open access to the labour market for EU member and non EU members .

In some cases, the lack of a work permit prevented migrants from pursuing their profession in Germany or to do training in Germany. A doctor from South Asia

was excluded from the German labour market for several years, as he resided with a toleration status and as asylum seeker. A female doctor from non-EU country who came as a family member of a Green Card holder was not allowed to work between 2002 and 2007. In 2013, when her husband obtained a Blue Card and the family re-migrated to Germany, she got a permission to work in Germany. A woman from a non-EU country who came in the early 1980s for political reasons had to postpone her training as medical assistant as she did not possess a work permit .

6. Measures regarding to the Recognition of qualification

As regulated professions, state admission to practise the profession in Germany is required for both doctors and nurses. Doctors need a full or temporary licence to practice whereas nurses need a state licence to practice as a general nurse.²⁹ These licences are granted in the course of procedure for recognition of professional qualifications. EU graduates enjoy more favourable recognition regulations than non-EU graduates. Whereas an automatic recognition for EU graduates is granted by the EU Recognition directive from 2005 (Directive 2005/36/EC), an individual assessment of equivalence of foreign qualifications with German standards takes place for non-EU graduates .

7. Coping strategies related to recognition Ans review Overqualification during recognition procedure .

During the recognition procedure some migrants were employed below their level of qualification. Migrant nurses from non-EU countries worked as nursing assistants with a corresponding lower wage, as a nurse from the former Yugoslavia and a nurse from Bosnia-Herzegovina reported. External stakeholders referred to cases of qualified nurses working as assistants for a long period of time until they achieve B2 language level, which is required for the recognition of qualification . (Kovacheva & Grewe, 2015) .

Conclusion

The healthcare workforce shortage in Germany is a multifaceted crisis demanding urgent and long-term action. Key drivers include an aging population and mass retirements among healthcare personnel. This demand is not matched by sufficient new entrants into the field. Universities and training institutions lack the capacity to train enough health workers. Working conditions in the healthcare sector are also increasingly stressful, pushing professionals away. Germany relies heavily on migrant health workers to fill these gaps. However, integrating foreign-trained professionals is riddled with challenges. Recruitment processes often sideline capable candidates due to administrative burdens. Work permits and recognition of qualifications are major obstacles for non-EU applicants. Support programs exist but are inconsistent and narrow in scope. Housing assistance and language courses are provided, but family reunification and spousal employment are neglected. Language barriers remain a core issue, limiting the success of training programs. Many foreign-trained nurses fail exams due to inadequate language preparation. During the recognition phase, many migrants face underemployment and poor wages. Works councils offer some support, but their impact is limited and reactive. Legal frameworks further disadvantage non-EU professionals, delaying full employment. This systemic underutilization of skilled migrants undermines workforce potential. Comprehensive reforms are needed to streamline qualification recognition. Improving working conditions and expanding educational capacities are equally critical. Only through coordinated policy changes and investment can Germany stabilize its healthcare workforce for the future.

References

1. Bonin, h., braeseke, g., & ganserer, a. (2015). Internationale fachkräfterekrutierung in der deutschen pflegebranche. Chancen und hemmnisse aus sicht der einrichtungen.(translation by author). Bertelsmann stiftung, gütersloh, 37-58.
2. Döring, a., paul, f. (2012). The german healthcare system. In: costigliola, v. (eds) healthcare overview. Advances in predictive, preventive and personalised medicine, vol 1. Springer, dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4602-2_4
3. Koch k, mikscha a, schürmann c, joos s, sawicki pt. The german health care system in international comparison: the primary care physicians' perspective. Dtsch arztebl int. 2011 apr;108(15):255-61. Doi: 10.3238/arztebl.2011.0255. Epub 2011 apr 15. Pmid: 21556263; pmcid: pmc3088170.
4. Kovacheva, v., & grewe, m. (2015, february). Migrant workers in the german healthcare sector. Hamburg institute of international economics (hwwi). <https://workint.fieri.it/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/background-report-germany.pdf>
5. Kovacheva, v., & grewe, m. (2015). Workplace integration of migrant health workers in germany: qualitative findings on experiences in two hamburg hospitals
6. Kuhlmann, e., falkenbach, m., brînzac, m.g. Et al. Tackling the primary healthcare workforce crisis: time to talk about health systems and governance—a comparative assessment of nine countries in the who european region. Hum resour health 22, 83 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12960-024-00965-2>
7. Lauxen, o., bieräugel, r. Der hessische pflegemonitor. Bundesgesundheitsbl. 56, 1056–1063 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00103-013-1744-z>
8. Svr (sachverständigenrat für integration und migration). (2023). Svr annual report 2022: core messages. https://www.svr-migration.de/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/svr-annual-report-2022_core-messages.pdf
9. Wahner-roedler, d. L., & knuth, p. (1997). The german health-care system. Science direct, 72(11), p1061-1068

10. Expert council on integration and migration (svr). (2022, may 13). A crucial component: the contribution of migrants to the german healthcare system. <https://www.svr-migration.de/en/press/annual-report-2022/>
11. Gill, j. (2025, february 14). In data: migrant medics plugging gaps in germany's health service. Context news. <https://www.context.news/socioeconomic-inclusion/in%20data:%20migrant%20medics%20plugging%20gaps%20in%20germany's%20health%20service>
12. Peters, f. (2025, january 8). Ärztemangel wird uns in einer weise treffen, die sich die bevölkerung nicht vorstellen kann. Welt. <https://www.welt.de/themenspecial/siemens-healthineers/article255071460/aerztemangel-wird-uns-in-einer-weise-treffen-die-sich-die-bevoelkerung-nicht-vorstellen-kann.html>
13. Protzman, t. (2025, january). Addressing germany's medical personnel shortage. American german institute. [https://americangerman.institute/2025/01/addressing-germanys-medical-personnel-shortage/#:~:text=germany%20is%20grappling%20with%20a,troubling%2c%20especially%20in%20rural%20areas.13.dw.\(2023,november1\).Germany'shealthcaresectorhitbyskilledlaborshortage.Dw.https://www.dw.com/en/germanys-health-care-sector-hit-by-skilled-labor-shortage/a-70800039](https://americangerman.institute/2025/01/addressing-germanys-medical-personnel-shortage/#:~:text=germany%20is%20grappling%20with%20a,troubling%2c%20especially%20in%20rural%20areas.13.dw.(2023,november1).Germany'shealthcaresectorhitbyskilledlaborshortage.Dw.https://www.dw.com/en/germanys-health-care-sector-hit-by-skilled-labor-shortage/a-70800039)
14. Times of india. (2023, april 1). Germany's health care sector hit by skilled labor shortage. Times of india. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/world/europe/germanys-health-care-sector-hit-by-skilled-labor-shortage/articleshow/115379423.cms>